

EXPLORING TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON RESEARCH IMPLEMENTATION GAPS AMONG PUBLIC SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS IN THE PROVINCE OF ILOILO

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Exploring Teachers' Perspectives on Research Implementation Gaps Among Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo

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Abstract

This qualitative study explores the challenges in research implementation within public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo, focusing on identifying key gaps and strategies to enhance research efficiency. A total of 227 Senior High School teachers from all public Senior High Schools across the province were involved as respondents, selected through a take-all sampling method. Using thematic analysis, the data gathered from respondents were analyzed to uncover recurring issues that hinder effective research implementation. The study identified six major gaps: (1) insufficient knowledge and research competence among teachers; (2) overwhelming teaching loads and multiple responsibilities; (3) lack of allocated funds and resources for research activities; (4) low prioritization of research; (5) absence or inactivity of research committees; and (6) incomplete or underdeveloped research policies. To address these gaps, the teacher-respondents proposed several strategic solutions, including: (1) providing targeted training programs, forums, and Learning Action Cells (LACs) to build research capacity; (2) establishing and activating research committees in collaboration with other institutions; (3) encouraging school heads to implement supportive mechanisms for research; (4) allocating adequate funding, facilities, and resources for research projects; (5) ensuring the full implementation of research policies; and (6) reducing the academic and administrative workload of teachers to allow more time for research. This study underscores the importance of institutional support, policy development, and resource allocation in fostering a robust research culture within public senior high schools.

Keywords: *research implementation, gaps, implementation strategies, teachers, senior high school*

Introduction

Research is a cornerstone of knowledge creation, playing a critical role in the dissemination of valuable insights across academic and scientific fields. Scholars and researchers worldwide rely on research to challenge, validate, or expand existing knowledge, contributing to the advancement of various disciplines. To ensure scholarly rigor and broader dissemination, completed research undergoes peer review and is published in academic journals, further enriching the global body of knowledge. For years, research has been a fundamental tool in academia, research institutions, and even private companies, serving as a metric for evaluating staff performance and productivity (Donayre, Casimiro, Casimiro, & Molina, 2020).

In the educational sector, the value of research extends beyond knowledge generation—it has a transformative impact on teaching practices and professional development. Ulla (2018) highlighted the positive influence of research on teachers' pedagogical methods and professional growth. Similarly, Demircioglu (2008), in his article "Learning How to Conduct Educational Research in Teacher Education," emphasizes that teachers play a pivotal role in the education system, with responsibilities that go beyond delivering the curriculum. Teachers must also identify and address emerging challenges within their classrooms and stay responsive to new developments in educational practices. This necessitates active engagement in educational research to enhance teaching quality. In many developed countries, teachers are increasingly expected to incorporate research findings into their pedagogies to improve teaching standards and solve classroom issues. The rise of Action Research in schools has empowered teachers to conduct their own research, fostering a culture of inquiry in the educational system.

Despite the recognized benefits of research, gaps in knowledge, skills, and infrastructure persist, particularly in the context of basic education institutions in the Philippines. Challenges related to research management, funding, and policy implementation hinder the full realization of research's potential in enhancing educational outcomes. Policymakers and educational leaders must recognize the critical importance of investing in research capacity-building and expanding opportunities for educational research. By aligning with global research trends and adopting evidence-based policies, these leaders can foster a more robust research culture within the education sector.

In response to these challenges, this study seeks to examine the research management processes in public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo. Specifically, the research aims to assess existing frameworks, identify gaps, and propose strategies for improving research implementation and innovation management within the Department of Education. Through this investigation, the study aspires to contribute to the development of a more effective and sustainable research culture in the Philippines' basic education sector.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study is to investigate the research implementation gaps of Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo for School Year 2022-2023. Based on the primary purpose of the study and the concerns discussed above, the following questions were developed:

1. What are the current gaps for efficient Research implementation among Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo?
2. What strategic options could these schools apply to address these gaps to achieve the intended research implementation objectives?

Literature Review

Research in Basic Education

Research in basic education aims to inform actions to be made through policy-making, improvement of practice in the classroom setting, and human resource development for effective governance. It is anchored on the following principles: (1) an academic tool in facilitating learning for Knowledge Building; (2) an aid to educational innovation in changing times; (3) a means to comprehend educational Issues and growth of public awareness on issues related to educative process; and (4) a mechanism in the establishment of the authenticity and veracity of classroom and workplace practices. From an educational point of view, research extends beyond having an impressive reward, for it develops both education practitioners' and students' critical thinking skills, analytical ability, and communication skills that are needed to become globally competitive. Educational research grew in popularity with the advent of the implementation of the K to 12 curricula, for it highlights the importance of connecting knowledge with practical application. In order to function well in educational endeavors, research becomes the lifeblood of operation to become effective and efficient in the quest of providing basic quality education (Arias, 2019).

In research and Innovations, the Philippines, through the Department of Education (DepEd) has issued Deped Order no. 39, s. 2016 for the adaptation of the "Basic Research Agenda," which promotes the "conduct of action research" in the country. The purpose of this is to identify teachers' and departments' concerns and problems and to recommend solutions based on the results and findings made. With professional growth and development as one of the key result areas for the individual teacher's performance commitment and review, doing action research has already become part of the annual performance appraisal for all teachers. It comprises five percent of the total score in individual teacher's evaluations. However, doing action research in the Philippine public elementary and secondary schools may not be equipped with the necessary knowledge on what action research is and how to do it. The Department of Education has been doing significant ways to update and inform public school teachers about the importance of doing research, but many teachers in both elementary and secondary schools were uninterested and demotivated. Factors like teaching timetables and heavy workloads (Morales, 2016; Kutlay, 2012) are just a few of the reasons why some public school teachers are not motivated and have no interest in doing research.

Many previous studies have proved the benefits research has on the teaching and learning process when conducted by teachers in the field. Apparently, there has been a growing number of teacher-researchers across the department and the world, including teachers who have learned to be teacher-researchers.

Pring (2000) noted that teachers' involvement with the research also has a number of benefits for professional growth and self-enrichment because it contributes to a new knowledge base and provides a reflexive learning experience. Smith (2010) has emphasized the integral connection between teaching and research and the need to develop teachers' ability to engage in a reflective activity as a part of professionalism.

In the study of Iliško et al. (2010), several findings were revealed on the integration of research in teaching and how this process was affected by certain variables possessed by the teacher respondents. All the teachers who are highly competent do not necessarily function at the highest level in all situations and areas of professional work at all times. Years of work and education do seem to be the most important factors directing teachers to engage with research. Younger teachers who are just entering the teaching profession concentrate on classroom management issues and the establishment of their position of power in the classroom. Still, they are open to experimenting, new ideas, and new commitments. Their research experience is updated after the experience of writing a diploma paper, but their initial passion for innovations appears to decrease very soon. Teachers with a master's degree and work experience of more than 20 years evaluated their competency to carry out research quite highly. They are mostly prepared to participate in improvement of their classroom practice; they judge the value of research according to applicative value and its potential for improving practice. Another finding in the one-way ANOVA test showed statistically significant differences between teachers with different periods of work experience regarding their self-evaluation of their research competency in the following phases of the research: planning the research, preparing for the research, processing the results, reflecting and presenting the research findings. Teachers' work experience significantly influenced the level of intellectual competency related to the stages of research that set the theme (ANOVA, $p=0.001$) and the process of the research (ANOVA, $p=0.007$). The lowest evaluation of the intellectual aspect in carrying out the research was among the teachers who had no work experience. During the preparatory stage of the research, the influence of teachers' work experience was on the level of a statistical tendency (ANOVA, $p=0.062$), but, in the stage of the process of doing research, the work experience had no significant influence on teachers' level of intellectual competency in doing research (ANOVA, $p=0.259$). Independent of teachers' work experience, self-evaluation of their competency for doing research in this stage was particularly high. The analyses of the influence of both, the level of education and the work experience of teachers were studied by comparing the competencies of respondents in five selected clusters. The lowest level of intellectual competency for all stages of the research is characteristic of the respondents in the first cluster who had a low level of education and no educational experience of work. The highest level of intellectual

competency was among the respondents from the 5th cluster comprised of teachers with a master's degree: 45% of respondents in this group had more than 20 years of work experience.

Several findings from the study of Iliško, et al. (2010) implies that the integration of teaching and research success depends upon certain factors: teachers' research competence, teachers' views about possibilities and practicalities of doing research, consideration of the teacher's workload and multiple responsibilities and roles, the supportive environment of the institution in which teachers work, the support and the encouragement or the lack of support teachers receive from the administration and a long-term institutional strategy for developing research-based curriculum in their schools.

On the other hand, a study explores teachers' perception and motivation, challenges, and needs of 50 teachers in Agusan del Norte, Philippines with regard to doing research. Findings revealed that teacher-respondents had a positive perception towards doing research and its benefits to their teaching practice and student's learning process. Thus, job promotion is the motivating factor why teachers do research (Alibagon, 2017).

DepEd Research Management Guidelines

In support of the Department's policy development process, Research Agenda, and policy and program development and implementation, the Department of Education (DepEd) continues to promote and strengthen the culture of research in basic education. DepEd hereby establishes the Research Management Guidelines (RMG) to provide guidance in managing research initiatives in the national, regional, schools' division, and school levels. The enclosed policy also improves support mechanisms for research such as funding, partnerships, and capacity building. This policy which is built on the gains in evidence-based decision-making from various education reforms or initiatives shall strengthen the culture of research in the Department. In addition, it improves the fund-sourcing mechanisms, and reinforces the link of research to education processes through research dissemination, utilization, and advocacy. This issuance repeals DepEd Order (DO) No. 43, s. 2015 and DO 4, s. 2016 and other issuances, rules and regulations, and provisions which are inconsistent with this policy.

These Guidelines provide guidance in the management and conduct of research initiatives at the national, regional, schools' division, and school levels to further promote and strengthen the culture of research in basic education. This policy also covers instructions for eligible DepEd employees in availing of research funds.

The legal framework of these guidelines is the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 (RA 9155) which mandates the Department of Education to enact policies and mechanisms through which the delivery of quality basic education may be continuously improved. The Research Management Guidelines (RMG) include the responsibilities of DepEd across all governance levels the undertaking of "educational research and studies" that will serve as one of the bases for necessary reforms and policy development.

Other frameworks of these guidelines are DepEd order No. 13, s. 2015 which established a systematic policy development process in the Department, promoting evidence-based policy formulation supported by research studies; DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2015 and DO No. 4, s. 2016 which set guidelines on the use of the Basic Education Research Fund (BERF). This policy outlined a clear framework for the implementation of a grant-awarding facility that had been underutilized since the issuance of DO No. 24, s. 2010 which originally made such grants available; DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016 promulgated the Basic Education Research Agenda, which makes known the research priorities of the Department across four themes (Teaching and Learning, Child Protection, Human Resource Development, and Governance) and three cross-cutting themes (Gender and Development, Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, and Inclusive Education) --- www.teacherph.com.

Research Processes

According to Bourke (2014), 'research is a process, not just a product'. Thus, the concept of the research process, which shapes the theoretical and conceptual perspectives, is closely related to research. Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias (2001) noted that the research process is a holistic set of activities that scientists undertake in the pursuit of knowledge it is a paradigm of scientific inquiry. In addition, it must be documented in publications within the field - this way, the value of the research can be appreciated, and stronger conclusions can be drawn from individual studies (Seuring, 2008). On the other hand, Vincent et al. (2002) conclude that the process is the key to the substantive and methodological evaluation of scientific research. According to Cooke (2003), the research process should attempt to comprehensively address the problem from the point of view of the scope of research analysis and the ability to support the implementation process through the use of selected management methods and develop the necessary objectives, theses, hypotheses, and research questions.

Research, according to Newman (as cited by Alibagon, 2019), is simply defined as a process of going about finding answers to unresolved problems and questions emerging from natural and artificial phenomena within our society and environment through systematic and logical procedures and techniques.

In the study of Alibagon (2017), Musa (2013) stated that research has been identified as the life wire not only in the teachers in the Department of Education but also in other fields of endeavor as it contributes to the growth and development of every profession. It could be argued that the only and best way to pursue knowledge development is through research. Research has significantly contributed to the economic development of countries like China and Europe. In the academe, likewise, research is vital to its

development and status.

Moseti (2015), as stated by Alibagon (2017), emphasized in her study that "Knowledge production through research in the universities rests largely with academic staff and postgraduate students, especially at the PhD level." With respect to Moseti's statement, thesis and dissertation are parts of the curriculum where students are compelled to produce research to finish their degree programs. Notably, in order to advance or sustain the HEIs' regional and national academic ranking, faculty members need to yield research output.

In addition, Tan et al. (2009) articulate that there is an increase in educational research in Singapore education institutions, which can be associated with the government's credence that research enhances education institutions' performance and nations' capacity to catch up in globalization.

CHED's research advocacy is best expressed in Memorandum Order No. 46 Series of 2012, Article V, which mandates universities to contribute to nation-building by providing highly specialized educational experiences to train experts in the various technical and disciplinary areas and by emphasizing the development of new knowledge and skills through research and development. The focus on the development of new knowledge is articulated through an emphasis on bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degree programs. Universities contribute to nation-building by producing experts, knowledge, and technological innovations that can serve as resources for long-term development processes in a globalized context.

Similarly, Vasquez (2017) determined the advantages, disadvantages, and challenges of teachers engaging in research. Among the advantages, one that is remarkable focuses on using research to improve the teaching conditions and the lives of the people in the community. As to disadvantages, the study noted that inadequate knowledge in doing research could lead institutions to implement off-beam plans and interventions. However, he found that there are more evident advantages for teachers who do a research study than disadvantages and challenges. He then suggested that administrators of educational institutions may carry out viable and long-term policies in providing relevant training to faculty and even students to be equipped to do research. Research is inevitable in the lives of professionals, especially teachers. The completion of successful research in the fields relies closely on the ability of the teachers to do so and on the existing research.

Thus, teachers should be trained and well-equipped with the knowledge and competencies in doing research. All trainings or workshops organized on action research were all knowledge-based. All organizations that facilitate these kinds of activities should evaluate the effect on the teacher participants. They must conduct follow-up training to allow teachers to be involved in the actual formulation of action research. They must also ask the participants to submit proposals for critique even after the training. This is to check if they were able to create action research upon returning to their station (Tupas, 2018).

Research Funding

According to Mayurama (2012), as cited by Alibagon (2017), a researcher commences his or her research work once he or she has availed of research funds. Moreover, Whitson (2012) said that universities are given large funds because they also conduct fruitful research, have excellent research facilities, employ competent research staff, and enroll graduate students. As such, one can deduce that the research grants given to a university would also influence its capacity to be research-capable.

Day (2010) recommended in his study that enough financial resources should be allocated and the budget allocation process should be effective so as to have the funds availed at the right time and be in the right hands in order to have the M&E processes a success.

Research funding is not only in demand in education but in all other fields, especially in health. Prudencio and Costa (2020) believed that the allocation of research funds should be equitable and sustained; lessons must be learned from past experiences of reactive, short-term funding to deal with pressing emergencies in order to prevent or control future infectious disease outbreaks. Combating this cycle of poverty requires sustained global commitment, including continued funding for the research community to enable the discovery and validation of efficacious and affordable strategies to tackle both the killers and a host of other infectious diseases.

Government funding for scientific research may influence the size of the research sector as well as the productivity of researchers within the sector (Jaycob & Lefgren, 2007).

However, Calma (2010) mentioned that funding alone is not always enough to encourage staff to successfully engage in research in both public and private university settings. Even in the case of universities where allocations to research are considerably sufficient, the underlying concern among participants, particularly academic staff, touches upon interest and motivation to do research, the rewards of research, and the required competencies to undertake research. Calma also revealed that the funding issue is not simply about having little money allocated for research and research training. There are some universities that have funds, even when considered low, found the issue to be more about capacity---the ability of universities to draw particularly from their staff the required expertise to undertake research and to train students in research. This implies that providing funding should not merely be about appropriating funds to support research projects but must also include provisions for research training of both staff and students.

Poor research competence will lead to a non-quality research output. Teachers with less research knowledge and skills to do research will not be able to produce quality work that is useful to the students and the school. This idea is similar to the findings of Ho et al. (2015): poor level of education among teachers will affect the quality of teaching and learning. Upgrading teachers' qualifications by

sending them to training and seminars should be one of the policy agendas in the education system.

Research Partnership

Research partnerships, including firms, universities, and, less often, government agencies, have grown in numbers and in importance in most industrial nations. Research Partnerships are complex organizational arrangements. They take many forms ranging from infrastructures to support the informal sharing of information among partners to the creation of entirely new research entities. Some include large numbers of firms joining together to set industry standards. Others are truly one-on-one research ventures with specific technological goals. Still, there are specific product-focused partnerships with either customers or suppliers aimed at solving a particular problem and thereby generating more business with just one other firm (Herzfeld et al., 2001).

Hoekstra et al. (2020) noted that conducting research in partnership with stakeholders (e.g., policy-makers, practitioners, organizations, and patients) is a promising and popular approach to improving the implementation of research findings in policy and practice. Increasingly, research partnerships in which researchers and stakeholders work together on a research project are becoming a widely accepted and sometimes mandated approach to research implementation. These partnerships aim to shift the research paradigm from one in which the researcher is the sole expert to one in which researchers and stakeholders co-lead research activities and collectively apply their expertise, knowledge, and skills within a team.

Moreover, Karimi et al. (2020) mentioned in their study that the performance of any program depends wholly on stakeholder engagement, especially the identification process, level of stakeholder involvement, and participation in carrying out the project's activities, which is very important in any organization so as to yield good results. The involvement of all the stakeholders in the program at different levels helps them advocate that they are the main beneficiaries of the project. Stakeholder involvement means bringing people together and resources to help them work as a team.

Didham et al. (2020) added that achieving the needed knowledge and resource co-production to advance policy and practice of sustainability education will largely depend on the involvement of relevant stakeholders comprising policymakers, education-related government officers, curriculum developers, and education practitioners in efforts to develop appropriate interfaces. Research partnerships increase community engagement. Thus, stronger collaboration and meaningful results could be generated out of community engagement.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) is described as a process that assists project managers to scale up performance and influence the results. M&E aims at improving present and future use outputs, outcomes and impact (United Nations Development Programme, 2012). Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) techniques help address the issue of measuring performance and achievement of projects. M&E has become imperative in all university programs and projects. No university pursuing development initiatives would proceed at all without an M&E framework in place.

Gyorkos (2013) asserts that monitoring provides management and stakeholders with clear indicators of advances and attainment of forecasted results using the available resources. It involves progressively and methodically collecting specific data as indicators in Public projects. Evaluation involves a well-planned and unbiased appraisal of a continuing or completed policy, program/project, how it is designed, executed, and the outcome. This is done in order to give, in good time, the appraisal of whether the program is relevant, efficient, and effective, whether it has impacted the beneficiaries, whether the interventions are sustainable, and whether it is in line with the purpose of its establishment.

According to Aden (2012), M&E helps those implementing programs to embrace decisions from an informed position with regard to how the program operates, how service is delivered, and whether the project is effective, using unbiased evidence. Aden added that M&E helps those implementing programs to embrace decisions from an informed position with regard to how the program operates, how service is delivered, and whether the project is effective, using unbiased evidence. Thus, feedback should be given immediately right after the program was implemented. He also added that the monitoring personnel should be well-trained to achieve the target of M&E. There should also be periodic refresher courses for the staff to keep them updated in their fields. In the course of the study, it was established that training has a significant influence on the project performance. This will enhance the efficiency and productivity of the M&E team.

Day (2010) advises that effective M&E is increasingly being appreciated as an important requirement for both project and portfolio management. This is because M&E provides grounds for being accountable in utilizing the resources available for development. Further M&E can be applied to make the project even stronger at the design stage, implementing it and stimulating potential partners among the stakeholders.

Project monitoring involves continuously assessing the implementation of projects with respect to schedules engendered during its design, inputs utilization, and services that are offered to those it is meant for. This is done in order to give, in good time, the appraisal of whether the program is relevant, efficient, and effective, whether it has impacted the beneficiaries, whether the interventions are sustainable, and whether it is in line with the purpose of its establishment (Simon, 2013).

M&E gives the project implementers useful information about the status of the project as regards tentative and final evaluations. Such information assists in identifying the required alterations, especially in the structure of the project, its impact, and the tentative date to complete it (Sinha & Labi, 2011).

It is very important to the M&E team to update research personnel, practitioners, institution partners, and stakeholders about the progress of the project they are working on. Collaboration with stakeholders and research partnerships can enhance the effectiveness of education policy research in dealing with context and complexity. In the case of monitoring and evaluation (M&E) of education for sustainable development (ESD), it can increase the identification of existing gaps when it is designed to “engender a process of both individual and institutional learning by creating an action-reflection cycle that supports the continual review of implementation and practice (Didham et al., 2020).

Monitoring and Evaluation are very important to those who seek to build a stronger research culture, they should have a clear and directed monitoring and evaluation system of research outputs as part of their investment plan for their academic endeavor. Timely dissemination and action should be taken if the redirection of research initiatives suggests otherwise.

Research Agenda, Policy, and Program Implementation

Policymaking, especially in relation to emergent fields of policy, may be understood as a process of social learning. While there are growing calls for efforts to bridge the science-policy interface to address complex socio-ecological challenges related to sustainable development, there is, unfortunately, limited actual debate on how to achieve these challenges. Weichselgartner and Kasperson (2010) propose to “Consider the collaborative production of knowledge as a systematic and emergent inquiry process, embedded in a collaborative partnership between scientists, policymakers, and practitioners to generate actionable scientific knowledge.” In the field of education research, the research is inevitably connected directly to both policy and practice and cannot be separated from these contextual factors. The relevance of education research is also closely linked to how it informs policy and/or practice, but bridges highlight that the issue of relevance is a challenging concept because what is relevant depends on the target audience, place, and time of application. Furthermore, existing research also shows that academic research is low on the list of sources that policymakers use to inform their decision-making and that they more regularly rely on information from commissions, trusted experts, and think tanks for ideas and evidence.

Based on the experience of facilitating a collaborative partnership for education research in this study though, we would propose that the involvement of diverse stakeholders in “checking” findings and recommendations improves relevance in a universal manner, aids in aligning priorities for policy and practice, and encourages greater ownership of the findings and recommendations from all involved actors. Collaboration among researchers, academics, policymakers, and practitioners at the research-policy interface of the M&E of the ESD research process, however, is not without challenges.

Weichselgartner and Kasperson identify three general groups of factors that hinder collaborative knowledge production: Functional factors, due to differing needs, objectives, and perspectives of actors; social factors that include cultural values and diverse professional forms of practice and communication; and structural factors like institutional settings and standards that can make collaboration difficult or impossible. In the experience of the case presented here, the collaborative partnership did have a positive impact on the functional and social factors that can limit multi-stakeholder engagement at the research-policy interface. Through critically reflective assessments and discussions on the practice of ESD and its monitoring and evaluation, the diverse stakeholders were able to coalesce their objectives and priorities into a more complementary arrangement. Through active participation and knowledge exchange, the actors developed appropriate means to clearly work together and communicate on these matters. While the case presented here did not have a lasting impact on structural factors, it did at least temporarily provide an alternative structure where active collaboration was possible among a diverse group of actors.

Research and Development Gaps in the Philippines

One of the factors that was found to be a significant determinant of productivity, in particular total factor productivity (TFP) of Philippine manufacturing, is Research and Development (R&D) investment. The rates of return to R&D investment in three major sectors in the Philippines. The sectors are (1) the primary sector – which includes agriculture and mining industries; (2) the industrial sector – which includes manufacturing, construction and utilities industries; and (3) the service sector – which includes transportation, trade, finance and other services. The rates of return to R&D investment are significant in both the primary and the service sectors, in particular, about 60 percent. These rates of return are higher than other form of investments like capital equipment and machineries, building and other fixed assets.

Research showed that the rates of return to R&D investment in other countries are found significantly high both for agriculture and industry, as well as for developed and developing countries. However, in the case of the industrial sector in the Philippines the rates of return to R&D investments are much lower, only about 10 percent. Admittedly, there are no well-identified and well-documented reasons behind this, but the closest one pertains to the severe lack of R&D personnel in industry which in turn leads to very low technological capability. Thus, with low R&D manpower capable of R&D work, any R&D investments cannot turn into productive results as desired. While the rates of return to R&D investment are high, there are indications the Philippines has been underinvesting in R&D. Based on UNESCO data, out of 91 countries, the Philippines is at the 73rd place in terms of the number of scientists and

engineers per million population. It has only 152 scientists and engineers per million population. This is far below the maximum of 6,736 scientists and engineers per million population. In terms of R&D expenditure to GNP ratio, the Philippines is at the 60th place with a ratio of 0.2 percent in 1992. This is far below the maximum of 3 percent (ResearchGate, 2022).

The economic costs of underinvesting in R&D may be substantial. Previous studies found that the productivity performance in the Philippines has not been very encouraging. In fact, Total Factor Productivity (TFP) has been declining. The declining productivity trend over the years is borne out in a number of productivity studies done at the macro level (ResearchGate, 2022).

The relatively poor productivity performance in the Philippines is one of the key reasons why it has not been able to sustain its growth process. The Philippine economy performed poorly over the last three decades compared to its Asian neighbors. (7.6 percent). Aside from the issue of underinvestment in R&D, there are also convincing indications of institutional inefficiencies in the national science and technology system in the Philippines which may have resulted in (1) a very weak delivery system from technology generation to adaption, use, and commercialization; (2) inefficient allocation of R&D resources; and (3) a complex and bloated system in the Department of Science and Technology. The point of interest is captured in the following question: If indeed the causality chain runs from R&D to innovation, to productivity and technological progress, and finally to economic growth and prosperity, by how much would the Philippines have to increase its investment in R&D (ResearchGate, 2022). Recently, the Department of Health (DOH) stressed that the Philippines should adopt policy-driven health priorities to better utilize the research being done in the country. Although the country's strong showing in a recent study by the Brookings Institution indicated the Philippines has a good environment for medical research and development, there is still a gap in translating research into policy.

Limited research production due to poor data collection and limited funds; low research credibility due to poor evidence; and limited appreciation of research to policy impacts as challenges affecting research uptake as challenges the government and healthcare sectors are still facing in translating research outcomes to effective policy. It was suggested that health priorities should be policy-driven to ensure that health research would be utilized through policy implementation. Research co-production and increased support for evidence-based research were also cited as strategies to effectively turn research into concrete policies. The policy documents must be able to capture the views and wishes of the beneficiaries, as well as the opinions of the researchers and testimonials. Effective policy research must be problem-driven, multi-dimensional, flexible, and strongly evidence-based, she stressed. The issue of policy adoption is a major challenge in implementing research-based policies; it is always prudent to consult with stakeholders/end-users (Philippine National Health Research System, 2017).

Addressing the Gap between Education Research and Practice

According to Boser and McDaniels (2018), research alone does not change practice. This is true in every field, be it engineering, education, or law. Studies are not enough to shift the day-to-day practice and habits of professionals; just putting information into someone's hands does not help them understand how to use that information to improve their work. Part of the reason is human nature; change is difficult. Another reason is that it takes work to make a study relevant to what's happening on the ground. Plus, practitioners are often skeptical of experts. Academics, after all, often seem far removed from the daily work experience.

There is not a linear pathway from evidence to decision-making. Officials in school districts or departments of education often struggle to find research relevant to their specific contexts. This issue is not necessarily a concern of the researchers producing the studies, and studies on a particular subject may have contradictory findings. Further, previously held professional experiences or beliefs, organizational priorities, and political demands influence how education leaders interpret this evidence and ultimately make decisions. Furthermore, a lot of attention has focused on "effectiveness" research to evaluate whether a specific practice or program, once implemented, affects an education outcome (Boser & McDaniels, 2018).

Boser and McDaniels, emphasized that policymakers have tried to encourage leaders at all levels to use research—largely by trying to improve the quality of research produced, making research more available to state and local leaders, and adopting evidence requirements. The logic behind this approach makes sense, but primarily focusing on research production and dissemination has done little to address the real-world challenges that keep education departments from using research. Evidence does not suggest that the dissemination of effective research in and of itself actually changes what practitioners do.

In addition, the latter stressed that in order for local and national school leaders to use research-based interventions to improve schools, there need to be policies that reflect how these leaders actually use research to make decisions. Studies have shown that practitioners prefer research that can inform their own improvement efforts, rather than effectiveness research.

This type of research can include traditional improvement science, but also descriptive analyses of how national issues affect a specific district or school, as well as the development of student on-track indicators or school climate measures to assess how students and schools are faring. Research focused on improvement is co-constructed by practitioners and researchers, and it is rooted in the challenges of practitioners' everyday work. Policy should support the creation of this type of research, as well as develop schools district' and national education departments' capacity to use findings to implement changes.

Methodology

This portion presents the method used in the study. Specifically, it consists of the following parts; (1) Research Design, (2) Respondents of the Study, (3) Instrument of the Study, (4) Procedure, and (5) Ethical Considerations.

Research Design

This research is a qualitative study using the survey method of investigation on the research implementation gaps among Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo. Moreover, the qualitative analysis on the current gaps for efficient Research implementation and the strategic options to address these gaps was also conducted. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data gathered in the study. Braun and Clarke (2006) state that thematic analysis is a foundational method of analysis that needed to be defined and described to solidify its place in qualitative research.

Participants

Included in the study were the two hundred twenty-seven (227) Senior High School teachers in the Division of Iloilo teaching research subject in the Senior High School for the school year 2022-2023. They were purposefully chosen to participate in the study. Excluded in this study are senior high school teachers who do not teach research subjects in the senior high school curriculum.

Instruments

The research instrument was the qualitative questions that gathered the current gaps for efficient Research implementation among Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo and the strategic options that the schools could apply to address the gaps to achieve the intended research policy objectives. The interview questions were validated by the experts prior to its administration.

Procedure

Permission to conduct was sought from the Division Superintendent, Division of Iloilo. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the researcher immediately scheduled the distribution of the researcher instrument via google form through the help of the Division Senior High School Coordinator. The Division Senior High School Coordinator sent the google link to the group chat of all school's Senior High School coordinator in the Division of Iloilo. Attached in the google link is the approved permit to conduct the study and the letter containing of the researcher instruction on how the respondents going to accomplish the research instrument. Upon retrieval of the accomplished questionnaires, the data were analyzed and interpreted using the thematic analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Before the administration of the research instrument, the researcher secured permission from Division Superintendent to conduct the study. The researcher considered ethical issues in the conduct of the study since professionals were used as respondents. Respondents were ensured of the confidentiality of the responses. This was explicitly written in the Letter to the Respondents. The researcher respected the rights, needs, values, and desires of the respondents. Moreover, the researcher was particularly cautious when asking questions that could elicit sensitive responses or questions about personal or sensitive problems. Furthermore, the researcher did not collect the names and e-mail addresses of the respondents. The data that were taken from them were kept private. The responses of the respondents were automatically deleted from the google drive and the hard copy of it were kept from the cabinet with lock; the only one with access to the documents is the researcher. In publishing the results of the study, the researcher would not include any information that would make it possible to identify them as a respondent. After the study is finished, all the documents with the data would be shredded to make sure that no data would leak and be used for deceitful purposes.

There was no conflict of interest that existed in this study since the researcher's decision to whom, how, when, why and where with regard to the conduct of this study are not influenced by personal interest. This is achieved because the researcher was not able to personally meet the respondents. The researcher instrument was administered through online platform and was facilitated by the Division Senior High School Coordinator who acted as mediator. The researcher only gathered the data through the google drive after one week upon distribution thus, the conflict of interest was diminished.

The manuscript was subjected to a plagiarism check by Grammarly. The findings were carefully examined, assuring an objective interpretation of the data. Extensive effort was exerted to ensure honest discussion of methods, procedures, and reporting of data and results.

Results and Discussion

Results of the Qualitative Study

The last stage of the Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis is producing the report, which constituted the final analysis of selected extracts to produce a report of the responses by the Public Senior High School Research teachers in the Province of Iloilo on their experiences of the current gaps for efficient research implementation.

Question 1. What are the current Gaps in efficient Research Management Processes and implementation among Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo?

There are two hundred twenty-seven (227) Public Senior High School teachers who participated in the study but there are only one hundred fifty-two (152) teachers responded in the qualitative research question number one (1) and their responses were grouped and six (6) themes were discovered, namely: 1) Lack of knowledge and competence with 41 responses and made up 27% of the total responses; 2) heavy teaching loads and multiple designations which is (31) 20% of the total responses; 3) no allocated funds or budget with 24 responses which is 16% of the total responses; 4) not given priority with 24 responses ; 5) not organized or inactive research committee which made up the 14% of the total population with 21 responses; and 6) policy is not fully implemented with 11 responses which made up the 7% of the total population.

Theme 1. Lack of knowledge and competence. Forty (40) Senior High School teachers shared the same sentiments that they don't have enough knowledge and competence to do research, which is the number one (1) pressing gap in their school. Why is it that the research management implementation is very poor? Knowledge and competence towards research is one of the most importance factors that needs to be addressed so that teachers will be able to do and implement research management process in their working fields effectively.

According to Respondents 6, 26, 28, 29, 34, 36, 41, 44, 49, 58, 60, 66, 71, 74, 80, 83, 86, 89, 90, 93, 99, 101, 102, 106, 108, 110, 115, 118, 126, 128, 130, 141, 148, 151, 152, 157, 160, 165, 172, 187, and 189 stated that in order for the teachers to effectively conduct researches "we should be educated on how to do research." "We lack of seminars and trainings about research." To conduct quality research, we need to enhance our capability and knowledge to unleash innovations and studies to compete and equip our learners in different strategies and become globally competitive learners."

All trainings or workshops organized on action research were all knowledge based. All organizations that facilitate these kinds of activities should evaluate the effect on the teacher participants. They must conduct follow up training as in allowing teachers to involve in actually formulation of action research. They must also ask the participants to submit proposal for critique even after the training. This is to check if they were able to create an action research upon returning to their station (Tupas, 2018).

Theme 2. Heavy teaching load and multiple designations.

Many respondents stated that the burden of teaching load hamper them to engage in Research. They perceive Research as an additional burden because of the multiple designations they need to attend to. Teachers with more capability in doing research in the fields are sometimes are also those teachers who were assigned to different multiple designations in schools especially in those small schools with less numbers of faculty. Thus, extra designations aside from regular teaching loads hinder teachers from doing and implementing research in the fields.

The respondents noted that in order for them to conduct research, they must be de-loaded for them to effectively do their tasks as teachers and researchers as well. Thirty-one (31) overloaded Senior High School Teachers responded the same way. According to Respondent 8, "Only few are conducting research in school because it is additional work and burden to teachers due to many school works." Moreover, the teachers view research as hard because they lack time. As Respondent 27 mentioned, "teachers are overloaded with teaching hours, no more time for writing researches."

Research is perceived by the respondents as an additional task because of too much academic preparations. Hence, "Research demands time which is difficult on the part of the teacher," as stated by Respondent 5, 25, 39,45, 46, 50, 68, 73, 74, 77, 92, 105, 107, 121, 123, 134, 135, 137, 140, 146, 162, 170, 173, 178, 183, 186, 190, 199, and 200.

The boundaries between teaching and researching begin to blur for some teachers and in some school settings. Still, the distinction between these two fields of work is a part of reality for most teachers. Hargreaves (1995) argues that there is a huge gap between researchers and practitioners. Researchers determine the agenda for educational research, but teachers assure that research has little relevance to classroom practice. This separation between teaching and researching is based on a view that both spheres of work have different aims. Research is supposed to produce new knowledge in most cases, while teachers are viewed merely as a tool to implement it (Iliko, et al., 2010).

Theme 3. No allocated funds or budget. Twenty-four (24) teachers stated funds are one of the factors that hold the teachers from conducting research. Funds are very essentials in doing research most especially in the implementation stage of it. Many researchers are hesitant of doing research because of financial incapacity to do so. According to Respondent 16, "Fund is always a big deal." Additionally, Respondents 7, 19, 20, 22, 25, 33, 40, 67, 71, 99, 104, 107, 127, 130, 134, 135, 137, 164, 171, 173, 185, 198, and 203 mentioned that "researchers have insufficient funds to conduct quality research and implement its results. The lack of financial assistance hinders the efficient and highly motivated personnel to manage the research implementation."

The findings were supported by Mayurama (2012, as cited by Alibagon (2017), it was found out in his study that a researcher commences on his or her research work once he or she had availed of research funds.

Theme 4. Not given priority. Research in schools is not given much importance which results to other concerns such as lack of facilities like computer units, internet connection, learning resources, and research archives. Researchers are motivated in doing research unless they are provided with the necessary materials and other needed things in order for them to finish the task effectively.

Many respondents pointed out that research activities are not given priority, twenty-four (24) teachers stated the same sentiments. As

stated by Respondent 40, “teachers are hesitant to conduct or involve themselves in conducting research due to lack of support from the school.” Respondents 15, 35, 47, 48, 53, 64, 65, 88, 98, 100, 109, 125, 131, 147, 168, 177, 182, 184, 191, 196, 197, 201 and 202 shared the same sentiments that research activities was not really a priority of the school thus, the best researchers were neglected since their research works will not be used in their promotion because promotion system is very poor and slow among public secondary high schools in the Province of Iloilo.

Research should be given priority because doing research is not only for the researcher to satisfy his personal desire to do research but many previous studies have evidenced the benefits research has on the teaching and learning process when conducted by teachers themselves. Consequently, there has been a growing number of teacher-researchers across the world, including teachers who have learned to be teacher-researchers.

Pring (2000) noted that teachers’ involvement with the research also has a number of benefits for professional growth and self-enrichment because it contributes to a new knowledge base and provides a reflexive learning experience.

Theme 5. No organized or inactive research committee.

The school must cultivate research culture. A research committee is essential to supervise and to spearhead the conduct of research in schools.

Twenty-one (21) responses were found that research committee is essential in every school to implement the research management process. As mentioned by Respondent 54, “It is difficult to conduct research because we don’t have research team in our school.” The role of the School Research Committee is crucial in facilitating the conduct of research. According to Respondent 158, “the school is just starting to reorganize the school research committee to address the research gaps.” Likewise, Respondents 3, 10, 11, 13, 24, 56, 65, 103, 106, 163, 167, 169, 176, 180, 181, 192, 194, 195, and 204 states that “our school needs research experts that will initiate in crafting research proposal.”

Research committee and other research personnel in school play a crucial role in cultivating the research culture among its colleague. This idea was supported by Goodall (as cited by Didham, 2020), it states that one way to improve university ranking is by hiring the best scholars and assigning them in positions of power such as: Research Head/Director, Dean or Department Chairperson. The hired and assigned best scholars will share their wisdom and experiences in research that will contribute in the development of research culture. Further, Goodall (2013) elaborated that “who would pay any attention to a Research Director with a few research and publication telling faculty members to improve their research output.” Goodall’s statements attest that Research Directors/Heads play a crucial role in the development of research culture. Indeed, good research management is needed to develop research culture.

Theme 6. Policy is not fully implemented.

Eleven (11) Senior High schools stated that the policy is not fully implemented in their school. Compliance to policy on conducting research is not fully implemented. Wide dissemination of information about the policy is very important.

As mentioned by Respondents 1, 14, 18, 21, 62, 70, 72, 79, 91, 114, and 156, “There is lack of implementation on research practices. Research in our school has not been fully strengthened. At times, Master Teachers conduct research for the sake of compliance alone.”

A study conducted by Biruk (2013) in Ethiopia affirmed that only a few teachers conducted research studies, because of the lack of teachers’ research skills and expertise. Although the teacher-participants held a positive attitude towards research, their participation and contribution were reported to be low. Factors like lack of research knowledge, insufficient research training programs for teachers to enhance and develop their research skills, and lack of reference materials limited them from doing research.

Some practical steps to encourage teachers to do research have been outlined by Grima-Farrell (2017). First, teachers’ needs should be looked into and provided so that their motivation to do research will increase. Second, research training and other research programs should be offered to teachers to equip them with the necessary skills to do research. Third, research collaboration should be emphasized so that teachers would be able to share their practices, skills, and knowledge. Lastly, support systems should be strong among teachers and schools’ management as doing research can be time consuming and tedious.

Similarly, Vasquez (2017) determined the advantages, disadvantages, and challenges of teachers engaging in research. Among the advantages, one that is remarkable focuses on using research in improving the teaching condition and the lives of the people in the community. As to disadvantages, the study noted that inadequate knowledge in doing research could lead institutions to implement off beam plans and interventions. However, he found that there are more evident advantages for teachers who do a research study than the disadvantages and challenges. He then suggested that administrators of educational institutions may carry out viable and long-term policies in providing relevant training to faculty and even students to be equipped in doing research.

Question 2. What are the Strategic options that the schools could apply to address the gaps to achieve the intended research policy objectives?

Out of two hundred twenty-seven (227) respondents of the study, one hundred ninety-five (195) enumerated strategic options to address the gaps on the research implementation among Public Senior High Schools in the province of Iloilo. Six (6) themes were discovered

and are the following: 1) Provide trainings, forums and Learning Action Cell (LAC) with seventy-two (72) responses that made up the 37% of the total responses; 2) Form research committee and collaborate with other institutions having forty (40) responses that becomes a 21% of the whole responses; 3) The School Head should provide mechanism with thirty-eight (38) and made up the 19% of the overall responses ; 4) Allocate funds and provide facilities, equipment and other resources with twenty (20) responses which also means 10% of the total responses; 5) Implement the policy with fourteen (14) responses which makes a 7% of the entire responses; and 6) Reduce academic loads with eleven (11) responses from the teacher-respondents that made-up the 6% of the total data.

Theme 1. Provide trainings, forums and include in Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions.

An efficient research management processes and implementation in schools could be attained if teachers be provided with necessary knowledge and skills to conduct research.

According to seventy-two (72) respondents, respondents 2, 6, 12, 13, 14, 20, 25, 27, 29, 32, 36, 40, 42, 44, 47, 51, 52, 59, 63, 64, 65, 67, 70, 71, 73, 79, 81, 82, 83, 84, 88, 91, 92, 96, 99, 103, 104, 107, 108, 111, 116, 117, 120, 122, 123, 125, 132, 134, 136, 137, 141, 142, 143, 144, 146, 149, 151, 156, 160, 161, 162, 163, 166, 168, 169, 171, 174, 176, 183, 192, 198 and 201, teachers should be allowed to attend forums, trainings, seminars and workshops to become better informed about research and innovations. These capacity-building activities could elicit a stronger commitment to conduct research and an opportunity for research to be disseminated in schools. Technical assistance is likewise helpful after the conducted forums or seminar-workshops to introduce the Department's thrusts, such as the Basic Education Research Fund (BERA) and the Basic Education Research Fund (BERF). This way, the teachers may understand the process and avail the education fund extended to qualified researcher-applicants.

A study conducted by Vásquez (2017) revealed that teachers do not conduct research because of a lack of research skills. Similarly, another study disclosed that insufficient research training (Ellis & Loughland, 2016) is a factor that hinders teachers to conduct research.

Another important avenue to popularize research in schools is by its inclusion in the In-Service Training for Teachers (INSET) and Learning Action Cell (LAC) planning to be part of the sessions conducted by identified LAC groups in schools.

Theme 2. Form a research committee and collaborate with other institutions.

A research committee instituted by the school could help develop a culture of research within the school, they are the one who could help teachers in implementing research policy and program in school.

Forty (40) Senior High School teachers in the Province of Iloilo stated that there should have a research committee to spare head the research activities in school. Respondents 3, 18, 37, 38, 39, 45, 56, 57, 61, 74, 75, 76, 77, 80, 86, 93, 95, 101, 102, 105, 106, 109, 118, 124, 126, 128, 129, 130, 139, 150, 164, 170, 172, 178, 180, 187, 191, 200, 208 and 217 suggested to establish a collaboration of teachers and other possible partners who are adept in research, especially by establishing a research committee or the research management team. It would also be a big help if the school could create a link with the Schools Division Office.

Various kinds of literature will attest to how research leaders' roles are invaluable in the development of research productivity. Thus, "Building a serious research profile does not happen without the deliberate action of executive leaders. Similarly, it is essential that all executive and senior staff actively support research development. While it needs to be led by a member of the executive, the whole task cannot be left to a one person" (Good Practice Guide: Developing Research Capacity, 2012, p. 2).

Theme 3. The School Head provides mechanisms.

School heads are agents of change who contribute a major impression on the educational milieu through their information-sharing methods, creating supportive social connections, participating in mentoring programs, and fostering progress (Aquino et al., 2021).

Thirty-eight (38) teacher-respondents suggested the same options on how to address the gaps in the implementation of research management processes among Public Senior High Schools in the Province of Iloilo.

School Heads should find ways to address gaps to achieve the intended research policy objectives, as suggested by Respondents 4, 15 and 30. On the same note Respondents 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 22, 30, 31, 35, 41, 47, 49, 60, 62, 66, 82, 85, 87, 89, 113, 114, 115, 147, 157, 158, 159, 175, 179, 182, 188, 193, 205, 207, 209 and 210 stated the importance of the initiative and support extended by the School Head to school's teaching and non-teaching personnel. The School Head should provide other mechanisms to support the research culture of the school, such as prioritizing research activities, providing technical and moral support, and requiring the conduct of research in every department in the school.

Theme 4. Allocate funds and provide facilities, equipment and other resources.

Many teachers in the Department are eager to conduct research. However, there is no provision of enough resources in order for them to materialize their eagerness to do research.

Twenty (20) teacher-respondents stated that the school should provide necessary materials and equipment, such as printers and office supplies, to the researchers. Respondents 1, 16, 20, 21, 23, 26, 33, 44, 50, 110, 135, 137, 138, 148, 184, 195, 196, 211, 214 and 216 suggested that to provide funds, facilities, equipment and other resources could really help in the implementation of research

management processes in school. Moreover, the respondents suggested for options such as the provision of a strong internet connectivity and soft copy storage of the researches. Other proposed facilities are hard copy storage of the printed researches for future studies and data collection purposes.

However, many studies have reported that one of the factors that hold back the teachers is the lack of financial support (Biruk, 2013). In a similar study conducted by Prudencio and Costa (2020), they believed that allocation of research funds should be equitable and sustained. Also, Jaycob and Lefgren (2007) believed that government funding for scientific research may influence the size of the research sector and the productivity of researchers within the sector.

Theme 5. Implement the policy.

Fourteen (14) responses suggest that the research policy should be implemented as to close the gap in the implementation.

Reforms in education have repeatedly been confronted with the challenge of policy implementation (Walshaw & Anthony, 2007). There should be a strict implementation, monitoring and evaluation procedures enforced to ensure the research activities of schools, as mentioned by Respondents 17, 54, 94, 97, 131, 154, 177, 185, 186, 190, 204 and 215. The Master Teachers, as suggested by Respondent 58, should be required to conduct research. Respondent 155 on the other hand, stated that DepEd should re-calibrate its implemented programs and requirements for teachers for them to conduct research. Finally, Respondents 186 and 215 indicated that there should be a reconstruction of research policy and guidelines as well as the guidelines and criteria for promotion of teachers.

Theme 6. Reduce academic load.

Eleven (11) teachers believed that reducing academic loads will allow the researchers to produce research works in the field.

Deduction of academic loads, other administrative loads, and coordinator-ships are what Respondents 43, 48, 78, 173, 181, 189, 194, 197, 203, 212, and 213 have seen as a factor in addressing the gap in addressing research policy objectives. Moreover, it could address time allotment and management conditions which constraint teachers to conduct research. Furthermore, Respondents 197, 212 and 213 opted to assign the administrative tasks of teachers to non-teaching personnel. To this effect, teachers may only have teaching loads, and proper time management and schedule will be observed so that they will have ample time to carry out research policy objectives.

Conducting action research is the most important activity for bringing changes and improvements in the teaching-learning process. The gap, however, is that most teachers admit they lack interest in conducting action research. Although there is an annual conduct of action research training and seminars, teachers are still reluctant to conduct for a few reasons like the lack of time, workload pressure, and other administrative work (Azarcon, 2019).

Conclusion

The study highlights the significant positive impact that research can have on teachers, particularly in enhancing their teaching practices. However, it acknowledges the various challenges that educators face in producing high-quality research and translating it into actionable classroom strategies. Time constraints, lack of resources, and limited research skills often hinder effective research engagement. Nevertheless, the commitment, motivation, dedication, and passion of teachers are crucial for overcoming these challenges. With the strong support of School Heads, co-teachers, stakeholders, and partner institutions, the successful implementation of research initiatives in Public Senior High Schools across the Province of Iloilo can be achieved, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in education. Moreover, it is recommended that schools establish a structured support system, including research capacity-building programs and collaborative partnerships, to empower teachers in conducting and applying research in their teaching practices.

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